

Targeting in vitro 3D models of glioblastoma with sinusoidal EM fields

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Abstract

The SUMCASTEC project aims to isolate and neutralize brain cancer stem-like cells (CSC) using electromagnetic stimulation. We present the main results on the effects of sinusoidal 30GHz EM fields on cerebral “organoids” as new reliable 3D models derived from primary cells of Glioblastoma Multiforme (GBM).

Glioblastoma (GBM) is the most aggressive type of primary brain tumor, characterized by the intrinsic resistance to chemotherapy due to the presence of a highly aggressive Cancer Stem Cell (CSC) subpopulation.

The coexistence in the same mass of bulk and CSCs stuck at different stages of differentiation add complexity to the potential treatment of GBM and suggests that heterogeneity in cell phenotype can result in a differential cell response to therapy. The identification of additional therapeutic strategies against GBM must therefore account for this intrinsic heterogenic nature.

Presented Work

In this context, recent evidence points at cerebral “organoids” as new reliable 3D models able to recapitulate the complexity and heterogeneity of the multiple cellular identities of the brain and of its microenvironment.

Moreover, the establishment and characterization of novel “GBM organoids” have been recently reported, thus laying the groundwork for the setup of “cancer organoids”-based studies, anticipated to better mirroring the multifaceted behavior of heterogenic cancer cell populations during the biological evaluation of treatment effects. Aware of this complexity, based on SUMCASTEC belief and long term goals, we generated in vitro 3D models able to mimic in vivo cell growth, by enabling their self-organization and multi-lineage differentiation, and allowing a mixed heterogeneity to exist within the culture environment and treated them with sinusoidal 30GHz EM fields. In particular, we generated GBM organoids (GBMorg), let them grow in a hypoxic microenvironment and evaluated their progressive structural organization and 3D conformation.

Cryosections of GBMorg revealed that GBM cells self-organize in an external cell-stratified thick layer with more internal cells arising a looser tissue conformation. Moreover, immunofluorescence analysis disclosed that GBMorg are endowed with different spatially-organized cell phenotypes with a diffuse strong expression of the neural stem cell marker Nestin throughout the organoid, whereas inner cells expressing high levels of the astrocytic markers GFAP and S100. Of note, we evidenced a peculiar distribution of the neuronal marker β -III tubulin, concentrated in the outer layer of the stratified cellular surface. As a confirmation, also the percentage of cells expressing the proliferation marker Ki67 in GBMorg was comparable to Ki67 indexes generally found in human GBM biopsies. 30GHz EM exposure of GBMorg from three different primary cultures has been performed with two different exposure modalities (CW1 and CW2) and effects in terms of structural morphology, phenotype, cell viability and transcriptional landscape evaluated at different time points after exposure until 72 h. Applied EM fields did not induce any significant alteration neither in GBMorg structure nor in phenotype at both early (4h) and late (72h) analysis time points. Moreover, in terms of viability, CW2 displayed moderate cytotoxic effects on GBMorg through cleaved Caspase-3 staining. Interestingly, analysis of whole transcriptome by Affymetrix arrays disclosed that both EM fields were able to strongly affect a cell cycle-associated gene signature, with more than 100 transcripts involved in the regulation of DNA replication, mitosis and cell cycle progression being significantly down-regulated after 24h from EM field exposure. Even if we should consider these results as a preliminary proof of concept of the usefulness of GBMorg as surrogate models embracing brain tumor complexity, they provide the possibility for exploring EM field-dependent effects in brain tissue-like structures in vitro. In addition, high frequency EM fields should be considered promising tools to be further developed in order to impair GBM tumor proliferation and progression.

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